

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ƏMƏK VƏ MÜHARİBƏ VETERANLARI İLƏ GÖRÜŞLƏR — GƏNCLƏRİN VƏTƏNPƏRVƏRLİK TƏRBIYƏSİNDƏ ƏN MÜHÜM AMILDIR

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MEETINGS WITH LABOR AND WAR VETERANS — THE MOST IMPORTANT FACTOR IN THE PATRIOTICAL EDUCATION OF YOUTH

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Xülasə

Gənclərdə vətənpərvərlik hissini formalaşmasında əlaqəli vətəndaşlıq-tərbiyə işləri mühüm rol oynayır. Xüsusilə təhsil müəssisələrində təşkil olunan müharibə və əmək veteranları ilə görüşlər gənclərdə milli-mənəvi dəyərlərə bağlılıq hissini gücləndirir. Bu məqalədə pedaqoji sistemdə vətənpərvərlik tərbiyəsinin əsas aspektləri, veteranlarla görüşlərin şagirdlərin psixoloji və mənəvi dünyasına təsiri, eləcə də bu təlim-tərbiyə tədbirlərinin praktik tətbiqi nümunələri təhlil olunur. Eyni zamanda, bu məsələnin dövlət siyasətindəki əhəmiyyəti vurğulanır, bildirilir ki, "Gənclər Azərbaycan dəyərləri əsasında tərbiyə almalı, Vətənə bağlı olmalı, öz tarixini, ədəbiyyatını, ana dilini mükəmməl bilməlidirlər". Bunun işığında veteranlarla görüşlər gənclərin milli şüurunun güclənməsinə və müstəqil dövlətimizin qorunmasına töhfə verə bilirlər.

Abstract

Related civic education activities play an important role in the formation of a sense of patriotism in young people. Meetings with war and labor veterans, especially those organized in educational institutions, strengthen the sense of commitment to national and spiritual values among young people. This article analyzes the main aspects of patriotic education in the pedagogical system, the impact of meetings with veterans on the psychological and spiritual world of students, as well as examples of the practical application of these educational measures. At the same time, the importance of this issue in state policy is emphasized, stating that "Young people should be educated on the basis of Azerbaijani values, be devoted to the Motherland, and know their history, literature, and native language perfectly".

In light of this, meetings with veterans can contribute to strengthening the national consciousness of young people and protecting our independent state.

Açar sözlər: vətənpərvərlik tərbiyəsi, əmək veteranları, müharibə veteranları, pedaqoji strategiya, psixoloji təsir, milli-mənəvi dəyərlər, gənclər.

Keywords: patriotic education, labor veterans, war veterans, pedagogical strategy, psychological impact, national-moral values, youth.

Introduction. Patriotic education is important for the stability of society and national security. In pedagogical literature, patriotism is described as a person's attachment to his native land, responsible action for its freedom and sovereignty. Although these qualities are innate, they require systematic education and upbringing [6]. The study of patriotic themes in the educational process, from schools to higher education institutions, strengthens the formation of national identity among young people. At the same time, the importance of meetings with veterans in the educational system is also confirmed, as such events form national consciousness by presenting examples of heroism to young people.

Pedagogical foundations of patriotic education

Patriotic education is implemented both through formal education (within the framework of subjects)

and informal (general education, mass events). For example, in history lessons, young people are presented with examples from the heroic pages of the nation. Studies show that in history lessons, a sense of patriotism, love for the Motherland and friends are formed in children; young people are ready to sacrifice their lives for the Motherland [2]. The assimilation of historical materials ensures the development of national consciousness, attachment to cultural and historical traditions in young people. For example, textbooks on the history of Azerbaijan contain examples of heroism, from ancient epics to modern Karabakh events. This plays an important role in the formation of the younger generation.

Main part. The Azerbaijani education strategy is based on the ideas of respect for national values. In this

regard, as modern and independent state-building develops in the current period, special attention is paid to the patriotic and military-patriotic education of the new young generation in schools [4, p. 26]. According to Parviz Allahverdiyev, it is appropriate to familiarize students with books reflecting the lives and fighting paths of our martyrs and to discuss these topics during additional classes. Such events create conditions for students to recognize our heroes who gave their lives for the integrity of our lands and to grow in a spirit of respect for them. On the other hand, being attached to our history, as bequeathed by war veterans, and being ready to defend the land are included in the content of national-spiritual patriotic qualities.

Pedagogical literature and school practice show that the basics of patriotic education are learned from the youngest grades: "Every Azerbaijani schoolchild should be prepared for military service in the future. Schools, youth organizations, and society as a whole should have the main responsibility in this direction" [1]. This idea shows the importance of preparing young people for the position of military citizenship. Thus, the pedagogical strategy is based on the cooperation of formal education, extracurricular activities and state educational propaganda institutions. Patriotic textbook content, the role of teachers and school events together serve this purpose. As a result, the national patriotic component in the worldview of students is strengthened, and a mature young person is formed who is connected to his history and heritage, aware of the duty of military citizenship.

The psychological and moral impact of meetings with veterans is undeniable. Meetings with veterans enrich the psychological world of young people and raise national pride. At such events, students get acquainted with examples of real heroes, hear about their path of battle and sacrifice. This strengthens national memory by creating a true image of heroism in young people. For example, Orkhan, a student of school No. 53 in Yasamal district, said: "When I listen to the stories of veterans, I feel that defending the Motherland is the duty of each of us." Studies show that the memories of martyr families and veterans give young people a moral stimulus and increase their sense of duty to the Motherland. In particular, communication with real warriors helps young people to better understand our national history. Students of the Faculty of Biology at Baku State University expressed that they had very mixed feelings after meeting with national hero Anar Mirzayev and veterans Vusal Shahbazov and Seyran Abdullayev, and that they were humbled by their courage. They wished such meetings would be regular.

International experience and sources also confirm that such meetings are considered important in various armies around the world. In the context of Azerbaijan, research shows that veterans of World War II are also commemorated - "It is necessary to remember the veterans who escaped from Nazi support in the World War. Veterans participate in a large part of military-patriotic events held in schools, they are the embodiment of intergenerational ties" [3, 251]. When students participate in events with veterans, they learn about historical events not from someone else's mouth, but from

living examples. Such contacts, according to child psychology, remain in the emotional memory and deepen the national-spiritual impression.

Listening to the personal stories of veterans educates students in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland. At the same time, they are motivated to prepare for combat. In this regard, the reports of the Republican Veterans Organization note that the experience gained from veterans inspired young people to liberate the occupied lands. According to the group leaders, "if it were not for regular meetings with veterans and excursions to historical places, schoolchildren would not know our history well in the future". Also, meetings with veterans integrate patriotism into daily life by involving young people in collective activities. Studies show that regular veteran meetings enrich the spiritual world of young people, instill in them a sense of attachment to the Motherland, and create loyalty to the civic obligations they have accepted [3, p.247]. Through communication with veterans, students experience the concept of national heroism, which affects the formation of their personalities, and also participate in the intergenerational transmission of the values of ideas, freedom, and patriotism.

Meetings with veterans are a widespread tradition in modern schools. These meetings are held in various formats - from classroom hours to festive events. For example, in one school, families of war veterans participated in a meeting with students and shared their memories, and students dedicated love poems and battle marches to them. At such events, patriotic messages integrated into the educational content are absorbed into the emotional memory of students. Other schools organize literary and musical evenings with veterans, where young people express their patriotic feelings through poetry. All these examples show that meetings with veterans reinforce the theoretical knowledge acquired during the educational process in a practical context and turn it into practice.

Special subjects in education also play an important role in terms of patriotism. For example, within the framework of the military-patriotic training subject before conscription, veteran officers conduct mutual exercises with students. As a result of these activities, students develop positive motivation and a sense of responsibility for military service and defense of the homeland. The student sees a living example from these meetings, makes that person an example and ideal for himself. Thus, veteran meetings in education become an active pedagogical tool that enriches teaching and creates opportunities for practical skills, and play an important complementary role in the educational process. In this regard, it should be noted that in order to form a patriotic spirit in young people, "theoretical knowledge of students and practical examples related to historical events should be harmoniously combined" [6, p.384].

As in all civilized states, President Ilham Aliyev has repeatedly highlighted the importance of patriotism in the upbringing of young people. In the summer of 2020, he said: "Azerbaijani youth should be educated on the basis of Azerbaijani values, traditional values... they should know their history, literature, and native

language perfectly and be proud that they are citizens of Azerbaijan” [8]. These words explain the main reasons for the priority given to national-spiritual education in state programs: our youth should deeply study and absorb the homeland, its historical and cultural heritage. Then he adds: “I positively evaluate the processes related to the upbringing of our youth in the spirit of patriotism. I see that a new, modern generation is growing up” [8]. At this point, the president states that the young generation born during the period of independence no longer grows up in secondary schools without patriotism; on the contrary, they will be brought up in the national spirit and determine the future of the country.

These principles are also a logical continuation of his meetings with veterans. In a conversation with a resident of Zangilan in the summer of 2021, Ilham Aliyev stated that “we have raised and educated a young generation with a strong love of the Motherland in their hearts” [8]. This idea is especially relevant in the post-war period - according to the head of state, the stories of veterans and our victory in the Second Karabakh War have shaped the national spirit of young people. With this statement, we come to the conclusion that teaching patriotism is not just a matter of textbooks – it also requires concrete examples. The living memories of veterans provide young people with companions to look up to, role models to learn from. In this sense, it is no longer a novelty for education: in addition to educational programs to strengthen national consciousness, examples of real heroes - veterans as mentors - should be included, and the Karabakh wars should be studied from all sides.

Conclusions and suggestions

In conclusion, it can be said that meetings with labor and war veterans are the main guiding component of patriotic education” [4, 247p.]. The learned experience of veterans serves to strengthen the national-moral bond in students, making them more loyal to their civic duty to the state and the Motherland. Such meetings increase the students’ sense of attachment to the Motherland, and at the same time form in them the will to serve in the army. As President Aliyev said, we are already “gladly seeing a new, modern patriotic generation” [10], and this generation was formed precisely by the example of veterans [8]. Studies also show that the heroic stories of veterans have an inspiring effect on young people, who approach the oath ceremony of readiness to defend the Motherland more responsibly.

Suggestions:

For the sustainable development of patriotism, it is advisable to systematize meetings with veterans. Thus:

(a) new textbooks and courses on history and patriotism at all levels of education - for example, "History of Heroes" - should be developed;

(b) advanced training seminars on working with veterans should be organized for teachers and educators;

(c) virtual platforms should be created to use technology to convey the stories of veterans to young people;

(d) inter-school projects and competitions should give special attention to the theme of war and labor heroism. These initiatives will strengthen the youth's commitment to the Motherland and ensure their development as citizens committed to national and spiritual values.

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